

Electrical Transformer Cable (Mini Review)

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Abstract

The operation of new electrical transformer cables is based on the principle of induction of electromotive force in an electrical conductor surrounded by a magnetic circuit. With the new arrangement of winding (or windings) in the form of cable conductors with a jacket, together performing the functions of the magnetic and protective parts of the transformer, the electrical transformer cable performs two functions: an electrical transformer and an electrical cable. In this case, the cost of a dual-use transformer cable is only the cost of one transformer or the cost of one shielded cable, which in this case is the same thing. The materials that make up the transformer are dual-use: one material is used both to perform the functions of the magnetic core and to perform the functions of the protective sheath (jacket) of the cable. As a result, combined shells–magnetic cores can be made from the same material with sufficient mechanical and magnetic properties.

Keywords: Power industry, Transformer, Electrical cable, Technology, Assembly, Economic effect, Transformer cooling.

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1. Introduction

Using examples of the use of the principle of EMF induction in an electrical conductor surrounded by a magnetic shell, the evolution of a new transformer and electrical cable in one device is shown step by step. The development of the transformer manufacturing and the manufacture of electrical cables from the first works of Michael Faraday [1] and Pavel Shilling [2] to modern designs of cable transformers and further, to the near future of cable transformer manufacturing is described. One of these new directions is based on the dual use of an electromagnetic transformer and an electromagnetic conductor (cable). In this case, electrical conductors and magnetic circuits are laid parallel to each other in the form of one cable. This ensures the use of electromotive force induction along one axis for two conductors surrounded by a magnetic circuit (cable jacket). This axis has at least two transformer conductors, which are covered by the magnetic core (cable jacket) of the cable. This is necessary to build a new transformer, both for the case of one phase and for the case of three phases of the transformer. A cable-shaped transformer has the advantage of cooling during operation.

1.1 History

In 1812, an electric cable was first manufactured, which was used to remotely detonate galvanic mines. [3] [4]

In 1831, the English physicist and chemist Michael Faraday discovered the phenomenon of electromagnetic induction, which became the basis of electrical engineering. Electromagnetic induction is the occurrence of an electromotive force in a conductor when an external magnetic field changes. [5] [6]

On this basis, in the same 1831, M. Faraday first described the principle of the transformer, and further clarification followed in 1939. It was a single phase transformer. [7]

In 1889, a three-phase transformer with a copper winding and an iron magnetic core was proposed. [8]

In 1889. Decision to use steel pipes to protect electrical cables while increasing the safety of electrical lighting of streets. [9] [10]

In 2003, designs of single-phase and three-phase transformers were proposed in the form of electrical cables coated with soft magnetic iron (steel). [11]

2. Methods

According to the principle of electromagnetic induction, a transformer induces electrical voltage in electrical conductors by changing the magnetic field surrounding these conductors. [5] [6]

Using the phenomenon of electromagnetic induction to change the ratio of currents and voltages in the primary and secondary circuits in the design of transformers. [7]

A change in the layout of the device is proposed, in which the determining factor is not the surrounding of the magnetic core by the electrical conductor of the coil of this transformer, but surrounding electrical conductors with a magnetic circuit. In this case, the geometry of the transformer changes: the length of the transformer is equal to the length of the electrical wire of the low-voltage coil, and the height of the transformer decreases a number of times proportional to the increase in the length of this transformer.

2.1. Development path of three-phase transformer

Initially, the three-phase transformer was designed using the properties of materials such as the best electrical conductivity of copper and the best magnetic conductivity of iron. [8]

In our time, a three-phase transformer with a layout that has become traditional has become widespread (see Figure 1).

Figure 1:

Source: Author.

Initially, steel-sheathed cable was designed to take advantage of the material properties such as the better electrical conductivity of copper and the better strength of steel (iron). [9] [10]

The new principle of constructing a three-phase transformer with a new layout (see Figure 2) contains the principle of constructing an electrical transformer cable. [11]

Figure 2:

Source: Author.

Here 1, 2, 3 are voltage phases terminals at the transformer input,

Here 4, 5, 6 are voltage phases terminals at the transformer output,

Seven (7) is the steel armour (magnetic core).

The terminals of phases 1, 2 and 3 are connected by electrical conductors (cables) to the terminals of phases 4, 5 and 6, respectively.

Moreover, the length of the magnetic cores in such transformers is equal to the length of the conductors of the low-voltage windings, and the role of magnetic cores in such transformers is

performed by iron cable protection. If each winding of a transformer consists of two parallel conductors placed in a magnetic core in the form of a pipe, then the parallel placement of three such windings forms a three-phase transformer.

If the transformer windings are made of copper and the magnetic cores are made of transformer steel, this will ensure the operability of the transformer. The windings of the transformer will act as an electrical cable, and such an electrical cable will act as a transformer.

Figure 3 shows the section of the transformer cable.

Figure 3:

Source: Author.

Here 1 and 4 are the electrical wires of the two windings of the transformer (cable),

Seven (7) is the armour (magnetic core) around the windings,

Eight (8) is the insulation between the wires of the windings and the armour (magnetic core).

In the proposed cable-transformer, steel armour 7 plays a dual role: a magnetic conductor and a protective shell.

The cable-transformer has a relatively large surface, which ensures its effective cooling, which is achieved not through a special cooling system, but through the original design of the cable-transformer.

2.2. Single-phase step-up (step-down) transformer

Figure 4 shows the cross-section of the step-up (step-down) cable of the transformer.

Figure 4:

Source: Author.

Here 1 is electrical wire of the step-down winding of the transformer (cable),

Four (4) are electrical wires of the step-up winding of the transformer (cable),

Seven (7) is the armour (magnetic core) around the windings,

Here 8 is the insulation between the wires of the windings and the armour (magnetic core).

Figure 5 shows a diagram of a step-up (step-down) transformer cable.

Here, 1 and 2 are low voltage side phase's terminals connected to each other by electrical conductors (cable) to form a step-down winding, as well as 4 and 5 are high voltage side phase's terminals connected together by electrical conductors (cable) to form a step-up winding.

Figure 5:

Source: Author.

5. Examples

As examples of development in transformer manufacturing, the prospects for transformers are considered:

- The isolation two-phase transformer, [12]
- The step-up two-phase transformer, [13]
- The step-down two-phase transformer,
- The step-down three-phase transformer,
- The step-up three-phase transformer. [13]

The length of the proposed cable transformer is determined by the length of the conductor of the low-voltage winding of this transformer cable:

- I. The isolation two-phase cable transformer will have a length equal to half the length of the transformer winding conductor.
- II. The step-up two-phase cable transformer will have a length equal to half the length of the conductor of the primary winding of the transformer.
- III. The step-down two-phase cable transformer will have a length equal to half the length of the conductor of the secondary winding of the transformer.

- IV. The step-down three-phase cable transformer will have a length equal to the length of the conductor of each secondary winding of the transformer.
- V. The step-up three-phase cable transformer will have a length equal to the length of the conductor of each primary winding of the transformer.

A cable-transformer, in the form of a narrow cylinder and a traditional transformer with a working volume, with the same power of both, has the advantage of a large contact surface between the surface of the transformer and the environment, which improves the cooling of the proposed cable-transformer.

6. Conclusion

At power plants, electricity is transferred from electric generators to transformer substations [14] and then to power lines via armoured electrical wires. The role of such wires and transformer substations can be performed by electrical transformer cable, in which the armour is made of transformer steel, and the cable wires act as transformer windings. This will ensure, when using the proposed transformer cable, a reduction in the cost of the transformer by the cost of the cable (transformer).

References

- [1] Michael Faraday (1791 – 1867), English physicist, founder of the doctrine of the electromagnetic field. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Michael-Faraday>
- [2] Павел Львович Шиллинг (1786 – 1837) изобрел электрическую мину. *Мегээнциклопедия Кирилла и Мефодия*. URL: <https://megabook.ru/article/Шиллинг%20Павел%20Львович> (Russian)
- [3] Самые известные изобретатели России. Автор-составитель С.В. Истомина. (2000). Москва: Вече. Страница 469. URL: https://allmines.net/e107_media/364aa377b5/images/Biblio%20articles/Istomin_Shilling.pdf
- [4] Дьяконов Ю.П. (2004). ПАВЕЛ ЛЬВОВИЧ ШИЛЛИНГ – ПИОНЕР ГАЛЬВАНИЗМА В РОССИИ (1786-1837) (Биографический очерк). Санкт-Петербург.

URL:

https://allmines.net/e107_media/364aa377b5/images/Biblio%20articles/diakonov_shilling.pdf

[5] Michael Faraday (1831). Tribune to Michael Faraday. Chapter XIII. Electricity from magnetism. P. 169. London. Identifier: b29976753. Lccn: 31016778. URL: <https://archive.org/details/b29976753/page/176/mode/2up>

[6] Faraday, Michael; Day, P. (1999). The philosopher's tree: a selection of Michael Faraday's writings. *Institute of Physics Pub.* UK, P. 71. URL: <https://www.worldcat.org/title/40559736>

[7] Faraday, Michael (1839). Experimental Researches in Electricity. London: Dent; New York: Dutton. (1914). URL: <https://archive.org/details/experimentalse00farai/ala/>

[8] Patent DE56359A Germany. Current transformer for alternating currents with shifted phases. 1889-08-28. URL: <https://patents.google.com/patent/DE56359A/en?q=DE56359> URL: <https://register.dpma.de/DPMAREgister/pat/PatSchrifteneinsicht?docId=DE56359A> (German)

[9] Thomas Edison (1889). THE DANGERS of ELECTRIC LIGHTING. *The North American Review*, 149(396), pp. 625–634. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25101896>

[10] Thomas Edison (1892). "Manufacture of filaments for incandescent electric lamps." U.S. Patent 470,925, issued March 15, URL: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US470925A/en>

[11] Суханов Владимир Николаевич (2003). Изобретательское творчество. Казань: Фолиант. ISBN: 5949900022, С. 115–116. P. 9 – 12. URL: <https://www.worldcat.org/title/izobretatelskoe-tvorchestvo/oclc/55576505>, URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/364354640_23_Kabel-Transformator

[12] Isolation Transformer. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/technology/isolation-transformer>

[13] Electrical Transformer. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. URL: <https://www.britannica.com/technology/transformer-electronics>

[14] Трансформаторная подстанция. *Мегаэнциклопедия Кирилла и Мефодия*. URL: <https://megabook.ru/article/Трансформаторная%20подстанция>

[15] Суханов Владимир Николаевич (2024). Электрический Кабель Трансформатор. ResearchGate. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22940.05761>